

A Survey on the Management of Electronic Records: A Case Study of Djibouti National Social Security Fund Main Branch

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Abstract

The effect of information and communication technology (ICT) adoption on the service management performance (SMP) of the National Social Security Fund of Djibouti (NSSF) was studied. The potential role of electronic records management adoption (ERMA) as a mediator was also investigated. Using SPSS software, correlational analysis, multivariate regression analysis and analysis of variance were done to understand the relationship between study constructs. Also, the partial least square design of structural equation modeling was used to determine the effect of ICT on ERMA, the effect of ICT on SMP and the effect of ERMA on SMP. According to results, ICT adoption positively influenced ERMA and SMP significantly ($p < 0.05$). ERMA also had a positive impact on SMP. Considering the mediation role of ERMA on the relationship between ICT and SMP, the indirect effect of ICT on SMP was measured. It was shown that ICT indirectly impacted SMP more than directly, hence the mediation of ERMA was confirmed. The implications of these findings are that, management divisions and policies that enhance investment and adoption of ICT are relevant infrastructurally to enhance the use of ERM systems in NSSF. Moreover, where ICT use already exists, SMP can be much more enhanced with the adoption of ERM systems.

Keywords: *Electronic records management; service performance; ICT; technology acceptance; technology adoption; organizational performance.*

1. Introduction

In recent times, managing records in an organization have been a thing that needs a lot of discussions. Globally, many organizations find it difficult to keep documented files or folders (Adams, McAra, Myers, Sheppard, & Withrow, 2004; Asogwa, 2013; Atkinson, 2020; Cook, 1994; Egwunyenga, 2009). Record management is vital to all institutions and if data are not correctly maintained, it is impossible to perform operations, compensate for what has transpired in the past, or make decisions about the future (Stewart, 2012). Records are a crucial organizational tool and must offer proof of intervention and decision-making (Shepherd & Yeo, 2003). The record is known as any kind of written material, irrespective of the physical nature or characteristics that an individual, entity or agency has produced, acquired or even retained (Clanchy, 2012). It is believed to be human memory extensions, intentionally developed to archive the facts, log transactions, express opinions, substantiate arguments, provide advanced explanations, provide justifications and provide permanent proof of events (Groth & Moreau, 2008; Head, 2019). That is why human beings need to build and store knowledge in order to recover and transfer it, so that concrete links with the past can be formed

The term record is referred to as records produced, obtained and retained by an entity or person as evidence and knowledge in fulfillment of legal obligations or in the course of business activity is well described by the International Standard on Record Management. According to the International Council on Archives (International Council on Archives, 1997), a record is characterized as documented material generated or obtained during the initiation, conduct or completion of an administrative or individual operation and containing sufficient substance, meaning, and structure to provide proof of action, regardless of the form or medium. On the other hand, the international standard association considers record management as a management area responsible for efficient and systematic tracking of receipt production, inventory usage and record management disposition based on procedures and systems for record creation, storage, retrieval and disposal (Gunnlaugsdottir, 2002; Oliver, 2014).

The application of electronic records management (ERM) procedures to ensure a more efficient management of social security funds is expected to improve service delivery in Djibouti. In Djibouti, Old-Age and Survivors Insurance Trust Fund and Disability Insurance Trust Fund (collectively, the Social Security Trust Fund or Trust Funds) are trust funds that provide government-administered social security benefits. The Social Security Administration receives payroll taxes and uses the revenue raised from trust accounts to support Old-Age benefits, Survivors, and Health Insurance. Social protection is more than a civil right and is fundamental. Social security also aims to address a wide variety of socio-economic problems and as a result, society is more robust. It is notably so where population distribution is ample and detailed. Access to social security has never been greater globally, and extreme poverty has declined significantly. Massive recent success shows the disparities in coverage are being bridged, but there are still big obstacles. As noted in the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals of the United Countries and as demonstrated in the implementation of national social security floors by the ILO, it is the responsibility of every concerned country to extend social security coverage; and this can be further enhanced and efficient through the adoption of electronic record management.

The Djibouti government is making efforts to improve on the existing conditions withing its national social security fund and has vowed to overhaul the pension scheme with a view to restoring financial security and strengthening management. The legislation was implemented as a core component of the Government's Structural Adjustment Program to restore fiscal stability, foster investment, reinvigorate employment, and improve social security programs. The government has asked the World Bank to develop a Pension Reform Strategy that will identify the major financial and institutional constraints facing the pension funds and explore options for restructuring. To this end, a World Bank team undertook a comprehensive analysis of the pension funds in partnership with the consultancy company IEM-ACTUARIAL, which was hired by the government to assist in the reform process. The department has collaborated closely with the numerous funds' executives and technicians and has immensely learned from their professional expertise. Given the extent of dedication and commitment shown so far, it cannot be said more that the role of electronic records is important in the efficient management of information as well as the sustainability and competitiveness of financial schemes and the NSSF of Djibouti.

Discussions on the use of appropriate technologies to enhance good practices and efficient management of social security fund records in Djibouti are relevant. Among many other challenges, many retired personnel and clients have complained of lost records which makes it difficult for them to benefit properly from their social security funds. These challenges have partly motivated this study. Other factors were concerning the sustainability and competitiveness of the National Social Security Fund of Djibouti (NSSF), given the fact that many other private firms have sprung up to provide similar services. The focus would help explain into details the importance of using electronic record systems to manage the safekeeping of information for future purposes.

1.1 Statement of the problem

A significant step in the growth of human communities was the introduction and implementation of structured social insurance programs for providing income assistance and medical treatment. The emergence of various forms of formal social protection mechanisms, ranging from voluntary group-based social protection mechanisms to compulsory contributory or non-contributory public social security schemes worldwide, testifies to the universal human need for social security and the importance of clear rights and entitlements. In this area, each record has to be correctly kept because each record is related or directly related to the satisfaction of the individual. Bake (2015) asserts that when one record is lost, it directly affects growth. Lack of access and inability to use strong management records can influence an organization's competitive success negatively. This implies that information in the form of documents is used as a strategic tool by organizations through workers to achieve a competitive edge for the company that produces, collects and uses it effectively (Elizabeth D, 2009). In his research on the electronic record management preparation of federal universities in Nigeria, Asogwa (2012) noticed that all workers in the registry divisions had never had any formal training in archive and record management. Management of electronic records and archives in organizations cannot thrive where the policies and infrastructures developed are not maintained by trained and knowledgeable personnel with archives and

records management, and the lack of appropriate and frequent staff instruction. Most record keepers and archivists in most developing parts of the world are not adequately qualified in the handling of documents. With no or little experience, they get appointed based on secondary education certification without specialized experience in archives and recordkeeping. From there, they move up the ranks to become record managers either by appointment or through seniority.

This study concerns the weaknesses and strengths of current electronic record management in Djibouti's NSSF and how it influences the service performance of the organization. The main challenges and areas of improvement in the forms of recommendations were also considered.

1.2 Research objectives

The main goal of the study was to ascertain the role of electronic record management plays in influencing the service management of Djibouti national social security fund. Specifically, the study sought:

1. To ascertain the relationship between ICT, use and service performance (SP) of NSSF;
2. To ascertain the relationship between ERMA and service performance (SP) of NSSF;
3. To assess if ERMA plays any mediating role on the relationship between ICT use and service performance (SP) of NSSF;

1.3 Research questions

The following questions were asked in order to achieve the specific objectives of the study:

1. How does ICT use influence SMP of NSSF?
2. Does ERMA influence SMP of NSSF?
3. Does ERMA play any mediating role in influencing the relationship between ICT use and SMP of NSSF?

1.4 Significance of the study

The information generated from the study may be used to improve the policy development process within the social security sector and as well provide additional dimensions for effective use of the electronic record management systems in organizations. Also, being able to define the current scope of adoption and use as well as the role of ERMA in SMP, it becomes easier for decisions to taken by other organizations regarding their adoption and support of ERMA. Further, having understood the scope, effects and challenges identified with the adoption of ERM in NSSF, the necessary checks and investments in ensuring the successful use of ERM can be taken into consideration. This will ensure that the benefits associated with ERMA are fully attained not only in NSSF but also in other public and private organizations.

3.1 Conceptual framework

A theoretical context is an essential component of research that shapes research quality and scope (AERA, 2006). In short, a theory is 'a set of interrelated structures, definitions and propositions to provide a hierarchical view of phenomena by identifying, explaining and forecasting interactions between variables' (Kerlinger F. N., 1986). Theory gives researchers an outline for making sense of their observations by providing a predominant structure to their studies. In this study, the effect of ICT adoption on SMP of NSSF was studied. Also, the effect of ICT use on the adoption of ERMA was studied as well as ERMA effects on SMP.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework on the effect of ERMA on the relationship between ICT adoption and SMP

3.2 Hypothesis development

Hypotheses are informed statements that seem to predict the outcome of objectively specific tasks set out to achieve the main goals of studies or experiments. Hypothesis development guides the study to focus only on those questions that matter and outcomes seek to either accept or reject such hypothesis. In this context, the various investigated relationships between variables and effects were supported by hypotheses based on literature.

Information communication technology (ICT) has been linked to the digital paradigm and has been associated with increased efficiency in performance and in the execution of activities regarding publicity, marketing, information dissemination, record keeping and archiving among many others. For instance, ICT has been shown to increase organizational performance in a number of studies (Chaudhary, Chaudhary, & Ali, 2020; DeStefano, Kneller, & Timmis, 2018; Kleinschmidt, Peters, & Leimeister, 2019; Loukis, Janssen, & Mintchev, 2019; Ul-Hameed, Shabbir, Imran, Raza, & Salman, 2019). As shown by the plethora of studies done earlier, if ICT has the potential to help organizations record and maintain data and information, retrieve and use information easily, reach out to customers easily without physical interactions, make payments and conduct many other transactions online through ICT, then it is acceptable to assume that the level of use and adoption of ICT may potentially influence the use and adoption of electronic records management systems. Hence, the hypothesis:

1. H1: ICT will have a positive influence on ERM adoption in NSSF; and

In a study conducted by (Janssen, Donnelly, Elder, Pathmanathan, & Shaw, 2021) it was revealed that a perceived positive influence of electronic health record to newly trained doctor had an opportunity to engage more actively with patient records and improve performance when ICT was applied. The management service of hospital saw a positive impact when workers experienced digital skills; and again, when in service training in ICT was provided to support their day-to-day activities, there was increased performance (De Leeuw & Woltjer, 2020). It was observed with ample suggestion that enhancement in service delivery is considered an important performance indicator of e-governance. (Alahakoon, 2020) If health care and government agencies elsewhere have seen a rapid transformation through the introduction of ICT and other e-services, then ICT could drastically change the SMP of NSSF. Therefore, it was hypothesized that :

2. H2: ICT will have a positive influence on SMP of NSSF.

Besides the relationships between ICT and ERMA and SMP, there is also the potential of ERMA to have a significant influence on SMP of organizations, including that of NSSF. Thus, if ERMA results from the investments made in ICT adoption and use, then it has the potential to also influence SMP in a similar but not the same fashion as ICT does. For example, the adoption of ERMA for medical records in a hospital was found to improve performance regarding the services delivered by the hospital (Alrehaili & Alsharqi, 2021). In a similar fashion, the adoption of ERMA in medical documentation helped improve on the services delivered by nurses in hospitals (Basyah, Lubis, Yunus, & Darsono, 2018). Some of the benefit attributed to these positive effects were the reduction in the risk of loss of medical record and ease in accessibility (Basyah et al., 2018). Therefore, it was hypothesized that ERMA in NSSF will have the potential to influence SMP as stated in H3.

3. H3: ERMA have a positive influence on SMP of NSSF.

A well-managed information technology system can be the way out to resolve the various question and enhance the overall performance. Concerning the mediation role of ERMA, influencing the relationship between ICT and SMP. It was demonstrates in (MahbulHye, Miraz, Sharif, & Hassan, 2020) that a good staff service quality, appropriate website design and well managed e-traceability system had a significant positive relationship with e-logistic companies' performance. It was argued that the improvement in all these three elements would eventually increase the firm's e-logistic performance. It can be said that the cause-effect relationship existing between ICT adoption and ERMA, gave the rationale that the mediating effect was possible. This is because there cannot be electronic record management without ICT involvement and as such, this may as well influence service management performance.

4. H4: ERMA will mediate the relationship between ICT adoption and SMP of NSSF.

4.1 Empirical Research Design

This study adopted quantitative methods of research to collate and analyze its data. The quantitative research method collects numerical data which are statistically analyzed (Aliaga & Gunderson, 2000). According to Apuke, (2017), “quantitative research methods answer questions on relationships within measurable variables to explain, predict and control a phenomenon”. The quantitative research method is an important tool for describing the relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study. Correlational analysis established the extent to which independent variables relate with each other as well as how each of them relates with the dependent variable. The independent variable in this study is electronic record management adoption and the dependent variables are service performance, competitiveness and sustainability of NSSF.

Figure 3: Diagram showing relationships between variables

The study measures the relationships between the variables as shown in Figure 5 above, represented by coefficients (a, b, and c). Multivariate regression analysis was used to establish the effect of ICT on SMP directly and indirectly through ERMA mediation test using PLS-SEM path analysis. Significance was determined at a *p* value of 0.05 and 0.01 wherever applicable at 95 and 99 %, respectively.

4.2 Data gathering instrument and mode of data collection

Structured questionnaires containing both close and open-ended questions were used to collect data from respondents. A structured questionnaire is one that provides fix responses for participants to choose from. It is a carefully planned questionnaire in which the items are constructed in a particular way to address a specific issue and in which the items for a particular group of respondents are the same (Kusi, 2012). The questionnaire was to be adopted to solicit the survey data which deals with investigating the occurrence of a phenomenon, practice or description of a program or event.

The Djibouti NSSF was the organization studied and questionnaires were administered to respondents by face-to-face mode and responses were collected after a considerably appropriate interval as agreed upon between researcher and respondent. This mode of questionnaire administration allowed for follow-ups and presented the opportunity for the researcher to provide further clarifications to respondents whenever needed. Questionnaires were piloted with a section of the study population (30 respondents) and anomalies were corrected before the actual empirical data collection. This was to ensure that all relevant questions were well understood by the respondents and that there were no ambiguities, typographical errors or abusive or irritating language that could jeopardize the data gathering process or meddle with the provision of accurate responses.

Data were organized and coded in SPSS (Version 25) and responses for all variables were measured using a 5-point Likert scale [(5) strongly Agree, (4) Agree, (3) neither Agree nor Disagree, (2) Disagree, (1) Strongly Disagree].

4.3 Sample size and sampling technique

The targeted sample size for the study was two hundred and forty (230) respondents comprising of all available staff of the Djibouti NSSF. This sample size is representative of the population because the entire population was targeted due to the rather small numbers. Convenience sampling was adopted such that staff available at post during data collection were engaged. Also, one hundred (100) customers were conveniently sampled to respond to questions related to service management performance of the NSSF, using customer-oriented questions as proposed in another study (El Saghier & Nathan, 2013). In all, three hundred and thirty (330) respondents were engaged. This sampling method used for NSSF staff satisfied the conditions for sample size determination at a 95 % confidence interval (CI) for a ± 5 precision rate (Dell, Holleran, & Ramakrishnan, 2002).

4.4 Data analysis

After the data were collected, they were carefully sorted and organized using IBM-SPSS (version 25). Excel spreadsheet. Further analyses were done using structural equation modeling, partial least square (SEM-PLS) design to establish the effects of independent variables on the dependent variables and the relationships between them using Smart PLS (version 3). A multiple regression analysis was used to check the mediating role of ERMA on the relationships between ICT and SMP as shown in Figure 4. Analysis of variance was used to determine statistical significance of values obtained using a 95 and 99 % confidence interval wherever applicable or a p-value of 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

4.5 Validity and Reliability

Validity means the instrument's efficacy or performance in calculating the particular property it aims to measure; on the other hand, reliability is the ability of a measuring means to produce reliable and consistent results. Kothari (2004) points out that reliability is the ability of a measuring instrument to give accurate and consistent results.

By comparing and reviewing data collected from the study through the questionnaires, validity was ensured that the data collected will be reliable and helpful in analyzing the data. Multicollinearity checks were done using variance inflation factor (VIF) of 5 as a threshold to validate the fitness of data for further analysis (Kock, 2017). The normality of distribution and residual plots of the regression model were also employed to ensure data validity and process reliability (Civelek, 2018). The Cronbach Alpha values for the measurements were also used to test for internal consistency of measurements (Sarstedt, Hair Jr, Cheah, Becker, & Ringle, 2019). Values above 0.7 were considered reliable (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Composite reliability and discriminant validity were done to test the internal consistency of data for further exploration and analysis using the PLS-SEM as reported in many earlier studies (Dolce, Vinzi, & Lauro, 2017; MATTHEWS, Hair, & MATTHEWS, 2018; Sarstedt, Ringle, & Hair, 2017).

4.6 Measurements

The measured variables of the study are grouped into dependent or predictor variables, which are electronic records management adoption (ERMA) and information and communication technology (ICT) and response or independent variable, service management (SM). According to multivariate regression modeling, the following model equation was used (Equation 1).

$$\hat{Y} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where β_0 , β_1 and β_2 are the coefficients for the constant, ERMA and ICT respectively. The variability in SM was determined by the output, \hat{Y} in Equation 1.

4.6.1 Electronic records management adoption (ERMA) measurement

This variable was measured based on the electronic management system adoption as measured by other scholars using questionnaire akin to the technology acceptance model (Hawash, Asma'Mokhtar, Yusof, & Mukred, 2020). Questions asked were scored on a 5-point Likert scale. Seven (7) questions in all were used to

measure this variable and these questions were loaded as manifest variable of the construct, ERMA. Consult appendix for list of questions and coding. Cloud computing services adoption questionnaire used to measure the level of adoption and use of the technology was modified for this variable (Asadi, Abdekhoda, & Nadrian, 2020).

4.6.2 Information and communication technology (ICT) adoption measurement

The use of ICT by the NSSF was measured as well using the technology adoption model (TAM) (Dube, Van Eck, & Zuva, 2020) approach with questions suited to achieve the objective of this study. The technology adoption questionnaire was developed to extract information concerning the ease of use, the infrastructural investment available, the technical skill set or expertise, fitness for purpose, frequency of use, level of satisfaction with use and functionality. In all, seven (7) questions were used to measure the adoption of ICT by NSSF. In many cases, and as backed by several studies, the adoption and use of ICT has many positive effects on performance of organizations (Atkinson, 2020; Boonstra & Broekhuis, 2010; Dincbas, Ergeneli, & Yigitbasioglu, 2021; Dube et al., 2020; Hasanain & Cooper, 2014).

4.6.3 Service management performance (SMP) measurement

According to some other studies done on organizational performance measurement, the subject is known to be crucial in organizational analysis as an effective tool for assessment (Dube et al., 2020; Min & Oh, 2020; Moura et al., 2020; Taşkan, Karatop, & Kubat, 2020; Tomioka & das Neves, 2020; Tran & Nguyen, 2020). Performance measurement can be described as a way of quantifying the efficiency and effectiveness of action, and this has helped in the improvement in the performance of organizations (Tran & Nguyen, 2020). There is an accepted challenge that is common to the measurement of performance at the organizational level, giving rise to different performance measurement frameworks such as service quality measurement (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985), the Sink and Tuttle model (Taşkan et al., 2020), the results and determinants framework (Brignall & Ballantine, 1996; Johnston, 1995), and the balanced scorecard (BSC) (Frederico, Garza-Reyes, Kumar, & Kumar, 2020) among others.

The service performance measurement (Cronin Jr & Taylor, 1992) emphasizes total customer satisfaction programs over strategies focused only on service quality as described by others (Parasuraman et al., 1985). According to Landrum et al. (2010) service performance should discard instruments related to user self-sufficiency and user satisfaction and focus on five key elements of service quality, such as service quality, system quality, information quality, user involvement and usefulness (Landrum, Prybutok, Peak, & Qin, 2010). Landrum et al. (2010) further identifies those additional dimensions such as individual impact, workgroup impact and organizational impact are also necessary to define system success.

Therefore, in this study, service management performance (SMP) was measured using customer-oriented questions related to the abovementioned areas that focus on service reliability, responsiveness and assurance. Six (6) questions were used to measure the construct according to an earlier study done to study service quality among Egyptian banks (El Saghier & Nathan, 2013) with some modifications in questions.

4.6.4 Scale reliability

The reliability of measurements and models is a characteristic that determine the ability to the process to properly explore the research questions in such a manner that results can be valid to be used for meaningful interpretation and statistical inference, as done in most studies (Agala et al., 2020; Li, Griffiths, Niu, & Mei, 2020). Reliability test was conducted to test the internal consistency of the study instruments used. Table 1 shows that the Cronbach Alpha values for the measurements were above 0.7, confirming high reliability and suitability of instrument used. According to some studies done, a Cronbach Alpha value ranging between 0.7 and 0.95 are preferred to lower values (Arulogun, Akande, Akindele, & Badmus, 2020; Paiva, Azevedo, Pereira, Garcia, & de Andrade, 2021).

Table 1: Reliability of study instruments

Reliability score of measurements		
Variable	Item	Alpha value
ICT	7	0.709
ERMA	7	0.811
SMP	6	0.727

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Sample characteristics

Samples were described according to age, gender, academic qualification and number of years of experience (Table 2). Descriptive results showed that 169 (73.5 %) of respondents were male and the remaining 61 (26.5 %) were female. This was an indication that the NSSF was male-dominated despite the general call for a shift towards gender parity in appointments in public and private sector organizations. According to age, 171 (74.3 %) of respondents were from 25 to 39 years, (51) 22.2 % were between 40 to 50 years and the remaining (8) 3.5 % were above 50 years. It was shown that majority of respondents were youthful and very few were older and approaching retirement age of 60 years in NSSF. In terms of academic qualification, 57 (24.8 %) had post-secondary education certificates, 99 (43.0 %) had first degree, 67 (29.1 %) had master's degree and the remaining 7 (3.1 %) had doctorate degree qualification. Also, data revealed that 82 (35.7 %) of respondents had from < 1- to 10-years work experience, 100 (43.5 %) had from 11- to 20-years work experience and the remaining 48 (20.8%) had above 20-years work experience at NSSF.

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of respondents

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Age	25 – 39	171	74.3
	40 – 50	51	22.2
	Above 50	8	3.5
Gender	Male	169	73.5
	Female	61	26.5
Academic qualification	Post-secondary certificate	57	24.8
	First degree	99	43
	Master degree	67	29.1
	Doctorate degree	7	3.1
Work experience	< 1 – 10- years	82	35.7
	11 – 20-years	100	43.5
	Above 20-years	48	20.8

5.2 Model fitness

Normality of data was checked as depicted in Figure 4a and the statistical fitness of data for regression assessment confirmed with correlation matrix for collinearity checks between variables (Table 1). Residual plot of expected verses observed data was also used to confirm adequacy of the statistical method used in this study (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: a) Residual plot of expected versus observed outcomes. b) Normality plot of data for regression model.

5.3 Correlational assessment of the relationships between study variables

Correlational analysis gave a description of the relationships within the independent variables as well as between the independent and dependent variables as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation matrix showing relationship between variables

		ERMA	ICT	SP	SUST
ERMA	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
ICT	Pearson Correlation	.306*	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.049			
SMP	Pearson Correlation	.740**	.491*	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.008	.025		

* = Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. ** = Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

The correlations between independent variables (ERMA and ICT) were weak but significant at a 95.0, but not at 99.0 % confidence interval (Table 3). Strong correlations were observed between the dependent variable SMP and ERMA (0.740, $p < 0.01$) and SMP and ICT (0.491, $p < 0.05$) (Table 3). VIF values below 2 for all variables showed no multicollinearity. These assessments have shown that the data are valid and can be used reliably to further understand the relationships between the variables studied.

From Table 3, it is shown that the adoption of ERM systems had the highest effect on the SMP of NSSF, with a Pearson correlation that attributes 74.0 % of change in SMP to ERMA. This was followed by ICT, with 49.1 % influences on SMP of NSSF.

5.4 Regression model

The regression model used for the analysis of data was significant ($p < 0.05$) and suitable for establishing the relationship between ICT and SMP as major constructs, considering the potential mediating role of ERMA. Regression model summary data which showed the coefficients of determination and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to confirm the statistical significance of the model. According to test statistics, R^2 and adjusted R^2 values of the regression model were 0.785 and 0.779 respectively, which showed that

predictor variables (ERMA and ICT) were able to predict up to ~79 % of the variability observed in the response variable (SMP), which proves the reliability of the process and validity of the regression model (Table 4).

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.791 ^a	.785	.779	1.10348

a. Predictors: (Constant), ERMA, ICT
b. Dependent Variable: SMP

Table 5: Model ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	152.067	2	71.228	23.839	.001^b
	Residual	90.552	27	2.988		
	Total	242.619	29			

a. Dependent Variable: SMP
b. Predictors: (Constant), ERMA, ICT

Table 6: Model Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.307	1.801		2.760	.010
	ERMA	.735	.119	.739	3.629	.001
	ICT	.488	.036	.489	3.013	.000

a. Dependent Variable: SMP

From regression coefficients shown in Table 6, the model Equation 1 becomes

$$SMP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

where β_0 , β_1 and β_2 are the coefficients for the constant, ERMA and ICT respectively.

Substituting coefficients into Equation 2 and doing away with error term, we have

$$SMP = 5.307 (1.801) + 0.739(0.119) + 0.489 (0.036) \quad (3).$$

This infers that for every unit increment in ERMA, there is a 73.9 % chance of increment in the SMP of NSSF, holding all other variables constant. This finding is in agreement with other studies done earlier. For instance, the effect of records management in mitigating financial risks and improving service management in banks in Nairobi showed that when record keeping management and practices were improved, risks were reduced and service performance increased significantly (Ambira & Kemoni, 2011). Other scholars have also emphasized the positive effect of ERMA on service delivery in various organizations such in educational institutions and corporate organizations (Mampe & Kalusopa, 2012; Mukred, Yusof, & Alotaibi, 2019; Mukred, Yusof, Alotaibi, Asma’Mokhtar, & Fauzi, 2019).

For ICT, a unit increment in its appropriate use has the potential to increase the SMP of NSSF by 48.9 %. This finding shows that there is a strong relationship between the use of ICT and the ability of NSSF to perform well in the delivery of its services to customers. Of course, it is expected that the use of electronic methods and systems to keep customer records and to sort and communicate customer details and other services results in a more satisfied customer base. Problems associated with the use of hardcopy documents such as loss of files, deterioration of papers, voluminous nature and lack of packing space, fatigue of sorting and searching for information, difficulty with data collation and analysis in non-electronic format and many others are no longer encountered (Ampofo, 2020). Time is saved as well as reduction in labour cost due to the need for fewer personnel.

Al-Busaidi and Al-Muharrami (2020) have stated in an earlier study that the benefits of ICT use in financial and other service-oriented organizations also extend beyond profitability (Al-Busaidi & Al-Muharrami, 2020). In today’s world of information technology, it is difficult to sustain organizations without the need for and the use of ICT for purposes such as visibility, marketing, customer relations, customer feedback, data collection, data analysis, advertisement and many more. The role of ICT in the performance of

agri-food supply chain sector organizations also revealed that ICT improved performance of firms in many ways such as bringing about reduction in inventory cost, improving visibility, marketing and sales, information dissemination and many others (Kumar, Singh, & Modgil, 2020). It is therefore not strange to have seen a strong positive correlation between the use of ICT and service performance of NSSF.

5.5 PLS-SEM path analysis and mediation test of ERMA

The use of structural equation modelling, partial least square design gives further details on the relationship between the study variables, especially, on the mediating potential of ERMA on the relationship between ICT and SMP. The usability and robustness of using PLS-SEM for mediation analysis has been emphasized in a study (Sarstedt, Hair Jr, Nitzl, Ringle, & Howard, 2020). To do this, the SmartPLS software (version 3) was used to analyze data using PLS-SEM approach.

To further explore data using this approach, the convergent validity of data was checked and factorial loadings for construct variables ranged between 0.66 and 0.93 (Table 7). The average variance extracted (AVE) was also greater than 0.50 and composite reliability (CR) was also above the AVE of constructs, showing internal consistency of data (Bacon, Sauer, & Young, 1995; Ringle, Da Silva, & Bido, 2015). Other studies have also shown that findings in this study regarding CR and AVE are consistent and acceptable for PLS-SEM analysis (Hair Jr, Howard, & Nitzl, 2020; Rodríguez, Villarreal, Valiño, & Blozis, 2020). Added, discriminant validity (DV) of constructs was tested according to the basis that AVE values of each construct must be higher than the squared correlation among the constructs (Al-Emran, Mezhuyev, & Kamaludin, 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2019). Using the oblique rotation of correlated factors, correlations that were below 0.6 showed discriminant validity (Table 8).

Table 7: Data reliability and convergence tests

Latent variable (factor)	Items	Factor analysis	AVE	CR	Cronbach's alpha
Information Communication Technology (ICT) Adoption	ICT1	0.72	0.58	0.75	0.79
	ICT2	0.69			
	ICT4	0.81			
	ICT5	0.84			
	ICT6	0.79			
Service Management Performance (SMP)	BDC1	0.77	0.66	0.79	0.86
	BDC2	0.66			
	BDC3	0.78			
	BDC4	0.85			
	BDC5	0.69			
Electronic Records Management Adoption (ERMA)	ERMA1	0.93	0.65	0.90	0.80
	ERMA2	0.88			
	ERMA5	0.82			
	ERMA6	0.68			

Table 8: Discriminant validity of factors

Factors	1	2	3
1. ICT Adoption	0.49		
2. SMP	0.57	0.53	
3. ERMA	0.45	0.47	0.45

From path analysis, ICT is shown in Figure 5 to positively influence the adoption of electronic record management significantly (ERMA) ($p < 0.05$). Also, ERMA positively influenced the performance of NSSF in the management of services (SMP) to a high degree. Considering the exclusive effect of ERMA on SMP ($r = 0.795$), it was able to mediate the effect of ICT on SMP from 0.405 to 0.651 ($p < 0.05$). Thus, the direct effect of ICT adoption on SMP was 40.5 % compared to its indirect effect (with ERMA) which was higher (65.1 %), a difference of 24.6 % attributable to the effect of ERMA (Figure 5).

6.2 Conclusions

In this study, it was shown that the use of ICT processes had a positive influence on the adoption and use of ERM among staff of NSSF significantly ($p < 0.05$). It was also found that the ability of organizations such as the NSSF to use ERM in the management of their services leads to improved service performance (SMP). Directly, ICT was found to improve SMP, but did more so through a direct effect through ERMA, which indicated a mediation role of ERMA. Thus, although ICT caused significant increment in SMP of NSSF, the adoption of ERM increased the effect of ICT on SMP the more than the exclusive effect of ICT.

By implication, management of organizations such as the NSSF should be able to not only invest in ICT adoption and use, but to do more to invest in the adoption and successful use of ERM systems for the management of their services and other organizational functions.

The researchers recommend that a further study be carried out to assess the moderating role of ERMA on the relationship between ICT and SMP. Also, future studies could engage a broader population and study subject other than limiting them to specific organizations in order to allow for generalizations and implementation of recommendations to other areas.

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